

Scope & Topics

Circuits and Systems: An International Journal (CSIJ) is an open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the Circuits and Systems and Applications. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of Circuits and Systems and Applications.

All submissions must describe original research, not published or currently under review for another conference or journal.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Analog, Digital circuits and Signal Processing
- Biomedical Circuits and Systems
- Circuits and Systems for Communications, Video technology
- Computer Aided Network Design
- Digital Communications
- Multimedia , Nano, Giga scale Systems and Applications
- Neural Network Circuits and Systems
- Nonlinear Circuits and Systems
- Photonic and Optoelectronic Circuits
- Power and Energy Circuits and Systems
- RF and Wireless Circuits and Systems
- Sensing and Sensor Networks
- Simulation and Modeling
- Test and Reliability
- VLSI Systems and Applications
- Advanced Technologies and Trends

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: csijjournal@airccse.com or [Submissions](#). Submission must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

Submission Deadline	: December 16, 2018
Notification	: January 16, 2019
Final Manuscript Due	: January 24, 2019
Publication Date	: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

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